

**SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINS FROM *o*-HYDROXY-ARYL-
ALKYL KETONES. PART II. FORMATION OF
o-COUMARIC ACIDS FROM *o*-HYDROXY-
ALDEHYDES.**

BY DUHKHAHARAN CHAKRAVARTI AND BRAJESWAR MAJUMDAR.

The methyl ethers of the *o*-hydroxy-aldehydes, e.g., 2-methoxybenzaldehyde, 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde, 5-chloro-2-methoxybenzaldehyde, condense with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl α -bromopropionate forming *trans*-cinnamic esters, which do not yield coumarins.

In attempting to synthesise coumarins from *o*-hydroxy-aldehydes by the method described by the authors (Chakravarti and Majumdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 15, 136) it has been found that *trans*-cinnamic esters are formed, which do not yield coumarins on heating with hydriodic acid or on keeping with concentrated sulphuric acid in the cold as in the case of the cinnamic esters, obtained from *o*-hydroxy-aryl-alkyl ketones. Thus 2-methoxybenzaldehyde and 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde readily condense with ethyl α -bromoacetate forming hydroxy-esters, which undergo dehydration with thionyl chloride in the presence of pyridine forming cinnamic esters but the latter do not form the expected coumarins. Ethyl 2-methoxycinnamate, obtained from benzaldehyde, has been shown to be the *trans*-variety as on hydrolysis it forms methoxy-*o*-coumaric acid, identical with the acid prepared from authentic *o*-coumaric acid by methylation and subsequent hydrolysis.

Similarly 2:4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde forms ethyl 2:4-dimethoxycinnamate, which on hydrolysis yields 2:4-dimethoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid described by Perkin and Schiess (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 86, 162; Tiemann and Will, *Ber.*,

1882, 15, 2079). 2-Methoxy-benzaldehyde on condensation with ethyl α -bromo-propionate forms ethyl *trans*-2-methoxy- α -methyl cinnamate as it is hydrolysed to *trans*-2-methoxy- α -methyl-cinnamic acid identical with the compound prepared by Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 415).

In order to study the influence of any group in the phenyl nucleus on the formation of *trans*-cinnamic esters, 5-chloro-2-methoxy-benzaldehyde has been condensed with ethyl α -bromoacetate and it has been found that ethyl 5-chloro-2-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamate is formed and the acid obtained after hydrolysis of the ester has been identified to be *trans*-5-chloro-2-methoxycinnamic acid by comparing it with an authentic specimen prepared by the methylation of 5-chloro-*o*-coumaric acid, which has been obtained in quantitative yield by heating an alkaline solution of 6-chlorocoumarin with mercuric oxide (*cf.* Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247).

The above experimental facts show that if there are no β -alkyl group in the resulting cinnamic ester, the latter has the *trans*-configuration. If the cinnamic esters formed have an alkyl substituent in β -position *cis*-configuration is obtained and these *cis*-*o*-methoxycinnamic esters easily form coumarins. The 2-methoxy-aldehydes, therefore, offer useful starting materials for the synthesis of *o*-coumaric acid derivatives in highly satisfactory yields.

The present paper also describes the synthesis of 7-methoxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin from resacetophenone dimethyl ether and ethyl α -bromopropionate. Resacetophenone dimethyl ether, however, readily forms ethyl 2:4-dimethoxy- α -methylcinnamate with ethyl α -bromoacetate but it does not form coumarin under the usual conditions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl 2-Methoxy-trans-cinnamate.—A solution of 2-methoxybenzaldehyde (11 g.) in sodium-dried benzene (50 c.c.), zinc wool (6 g.) and

ethyl α -bromoacetate (16 g.) was heated on the water-bath for about 2 hours and the solution poured into ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid. The benzene layer was removed, washed with soda solution and then with water, dried, benzene removed and ethyl β -hydroxy- β -(2-methoxy)-phenylpropionate distilled at 150-54°/10 mm. as a colourless thick oil, yield 11 g. The condensation product (11 g.), thus obtained, was converted into the unsaturated ester with thionyl chloride (6 g.) in the presence of pyridine (9 g.) in dry ethereal solution. After decomposing the excess of thionyl chloride with ice the ethereal layer was washed with hydrochloric acid, alkali and then with water. On removing ether ethyl 2-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamate was distilled at 150°/8 mm., yield 10 g. (Found: C, 69.8; H, 6.7. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 69.9; H, 6.79 per cent).

2-Methoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid was obtained by the hydrolysis of the above ester with alcoholic potash. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 182°. It was identified as 2-methoxy-*trans*-cinnamic acid by preparing an authentic specimen from *o*-coumaric acid, which was methylated by means of dimethyl sulphate and the methyl methoxy-*o*-coumarate hydrolysed by alkali. The two specimens were identical in all respects (m.p. and mixed m.p. 182°).

*Ethyl 2-Methoxy- α -methyl-*trans*-cinnamate.*—Ethyl α -methyl- β -hydroxy- β -(2-methoxy)-phenylpropionate, b.p. 155°/4 mm. was obtained by submitting 2-methoxybenzaldehyde (6 g.) and ethyl α -bromopropionate (6 g.) to Reformatsky's reaction in the presence of zinc wool (3 g.), yield 6 g. It was converted into ethyl 2-methoxy- α -methyl-*trans*-cinnamate with thionyl chloride (8 g.) in the presence of pyridine (5 g.) in the usual manner, b.p. 150-55°/4 mm.

trans-2-Methoxy- α -methylcinnamic acid, m.p. 102°, was obtained by the hydrolysis of the above compound with alcoholic potash (*cf.* Perkin, *loc. cit.*).

*Ethyl 2 : 4-Dimethoxy-*trans*-cinnamate.*—Ethyl β -hydroxy- β -(2 : 4-dimethoxy)-phenylpropionate, the condensation product of 2 : 4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (6.6 g.) and ethyl α -bromoacetate (8 g.) using zinc wool (4 g.), was obtained as a thick colourless oil, b.p. 180-84°/8 mm., yield 6 g. It was dehydrated with thionyl chloride and pyridine in the usual manner giving the cinnamic ester, b.p. 180-184°/8 mm.

trans-2:4-Dimethoxycinnamic acid, m.p. 184°, was obtained by the hydrolysis of the above ester with alcoholic potash. It is identical with the compound described by Perkin and Schiess (*loc. cit.*).

*Ethyl 2-Methoxy-5-chloro-*trans*-cinnamate.*—Ethyl β -hydroxy- β -(2-methoxy-5-chloro)-phenylpropionate, b.p. 185°/4 mm., was obtained by condensing 2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzaldehyde (8.5 g.), ethyl α -bromoacetate

(8.5 g.) using zinc wool (4 g.) as usual. The propionate (8 g.) was dehydrated with thionyl chloride (4 g.) in the presence of pyridine (6 g.), when the cinnamate was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. $170^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found: Cl, 14.3. $C_{12}H_{13}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.76 per cent).

trans-5-Chloro-2-methoxycinnamic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the above ester with potash. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 191° . It was identified with a sample of an authentic acid having the *trans*-configuration. 5-Chloro-*o*-coumaric acid, m.p. 190° , was prepared from 6-chloro-coumarin by mercuric oxide according to the method of Sen and Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*). It was then methylated with dimethyl sulphate and alkali and the resulting methyl 5-chloro-2-methoxy-*o*-coumarate hydrolysed with alcoholic potash giving *trans*-5-chloro-2-methoxycinnamic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 191° .

Ethyl 2:4-dimethoxy- $\alpha\beta$ -dimethylcinnamate was prepared by condensing resacetophenone dimethyl ether (10 g.), ethyl α -bromopropionate (9 g.) using zinc wool (4 g.). The unsaturated ester was formed by dehydration during vacuum distillation. It boils at $180-82^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 8.5 g. 3:4-Dimethyl-7-methoxycoumarin was obtained by mixing the above compound with sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) in the cold and allowing to stand overnight. The solution was poured into powdered ice and the solid separating was collected and crystallised from alcohol as colourless silky needles, m.p. 140° (not depressed when mixed with an authentic specimen). 3:4-Dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin was also obtained by heating ethyl 2:4-dimethoxy- $\alpha\beta$ -dimethylcinnamate (1 g.) with hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7, 7 c.c.) at 140° for 2 hours. The mixture was poured into water and the solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 256° , the m.p. being not depressed when mixed with an authentic sample.

Ethyl 2:4-dimethoxy- β -methylcinnamate was prepared by reacting resacetophenone dimethyl ether (10 g.), ethyl α -bromoacetate using zinc wool (4 g.). The hydroxy-ester was dehydrated during vacuum distillation. It was obtained as a light yellow oil, b.p. $174^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 9 g. 2:4-Dimethoxy- β -methylcinnamic acid, m.p. 145° , was readily obtained by the hydrolysis of the above ester, identical with the acid described by Pechmann and Cohen (*Ber.*, 1884 17, 2132). It has not been possible to effect the ring-closure of the above ester either by heating with hydriodic acid or with cold concentrated sulphuric acid as the oily product obtained could not be crystallised.